

ESTIMATING UNCERTAINTY LIMITS IN THE NIST-2008 ELECTRONIC KILOGRAM

R. L. Steiner, E. R. Williams, R. Liu, and B. Parker*
National Institute of Standards and Technology[†]
Gaithersburg, MD

Abstract

The NIST electronic kilogram has had three published results with successively smaller uncertainties. In the present design, there are several measurement components that have uncertainties that are difficult to reduce further. These limiting uncertainties are discussed.

Introduction

The watt balance technique [1] has been considered as a replacement definition for the unit of mass, the kilogram [2]. The system measures the relation of atomic clock time, laser length, Josephson voltage, quantum Hall resistance, and the Planck constant h to artifact mass. This is done by balancing a mass with an induction coil in a magnetic field and measuring the force/current F/I ratio, and then moving the coil and measuring the voltage/velocity U/v ratio. The complete relation is

$$(mgv)/(U^2/Z)_{90} (1/K_{J-90}^2 R_{K-90}) = h/4 \quad (1)$$

where m is a mass reference, Z is a resistance reference, g is the acceleration of gravity, K_{J-90} is the conventional value of the Josephson constant, and R_{K-90} is the conventional value of the von Klitzing constant. U and Z are measured in 1990 units. Details of this experiment have been covered elsewhere [3]. The most recent result for h is $6.62606895(24) \times 10^{-34}$ J-s[4].

To be viable as a means to realize a new definition for a unit kilogram, a system must have reasonable uncertainty and be reproducible over many years. We will discuss here both the few uncertainty sources that appear to be preventing the reduction of the combined relative standard uncertainty of the system to below 20 parts in 10^9 and the 3 yr reproducibility of this system.

*Currently Massachusetts Institute of Technology

[†]Quantum Electrical Metrology Division, Electronics and Electrical Engineering Laboratory, U.S. Department of Commerce. Official contribution of the National Institute of Standards and Technology, not subject to copyright in the United States.

Limiting Sources of Uncertainty

The uncertainty components in the electronic kilogram can be placed into three groups. These uncertainties relate to: the value of references, alignment corrections, and long term changes in the watt ratios that suggest some unknown systematic effects.

Reference uncertainties

The acceleration of gravity (g) is the most uncertain of the reference values, mainly because it has been difficult to periodically perform all the necessary measurements. In a more comprehensive absolute measurement and transfer, a g value with a combined relative uncertainty of $0.0084 \mu\text{W}/\text{W}$ (units equivalent contribution to watt value) was measured.

Four 100Ω resistance references used in this system must be transferred periodically to another building for calibration. The resistors show nearly linearly predictable behavior within $0.015 \mu\text{W}/\text{W}$ uncertainty, but only for about 2 yr back in time. Additionally, these resistors have or were equipped with BPO connectors for quick connectivity, but the connectors have occasionally added noise and offset to the force current measurement. The solution has been simply to break and reconnect; the cause is as yet unknown.

Finally, the mass reference has a small positive drift in the value over the past 3 years. It is undergoing wear from the force balance operations, about 150 mass placements per nightly run, but it has also not been cleaned. Without a longer history, the uncertainty of the mass value is at least $0.01 \mu\text{W}/\text{W}$.

Alignment corrections

There are about 8 terms for applying alignment corrections due to motion of the induction coil. The largest but most straightforward of these corrects for motion in the X - Y -plane. There is a variation from changes in the magnetic field of the U/v values of 2.4 and $6.5 \mu\text{W}/\text{W}/\text{mm}$ along the (east) X - and (north) Y -axes respectively. It is easily measured by taking velocity mode measurements at different X - Y positions of up to 1 mm from nominal. Motion of a few micrometers during normal runs results from a displacement between the velocity mode and force mode. The motion sensing system has a resolution of about $1 \mu\text{m}$.

The remaining corrections are more difficult to calibrate, having to do with force and velocity vector dot products for off-Z-axis motion of the coil. A term that relates horizontal motions during velocity and force mode has been argued as being redundant within normal watt measurements. A term that relates coil torques in force mode relative to changes in angle during velocity is also not possible to check independently. Although the average tilt is small, coil tilting is induced at the start of each velocity pass and is very synchronous over many passes, so the actual correction factor may be much higher than expected.

Long Term Effects

The magnetic flux density is not uniform along the Z-axis, and so the U/v ratio has an M-shaped profile that requires at least 8th order modeling. The U/v profile also has noise of 10 $\mu\text{W}/\text{W}$ peak-peak or more at frequencies greater than 1 Hz. It has been found that at least in short term, daily or weekly behavior, the choice of modeling order can offset the watt value by 0.015 $\mu\text{W}/\text{W}$. Until the excess noise (generally related to ground vibration) can be reduced, it is unlikely this uncertainty can be reduced.

Occasionally the watt ratio values shift by an amount significantly greater than the typical standard deviation. Sometimes these outliers occur during identifiable extremes in operating conditions: coil misalignments, room temperature changes, or magnetic field drifts. Although the watt variations can sometimes be coincident with these extreme conditions, the scale or mechanism of the effects are not predictable and thus have no correction factor.

Conclusion: Long Term Reproducibility

This experiment has been run in roughly the same configuration for 3 years. Each watt ratio point is the average of a run consisting of 5 to 45 points, usually about 10 to 15 per night. The average value of all these watt data points, represented as the ratio of watt units ($W_{90}/W - 1$), is 0.035 $\mu\text{W}/\text{W}$. (Not all corrections have been updated and applied.) We prefer to use the normal standard deviation (SD) of ± 0.014 $\mu\text{W}/\text{W}$ of the averaged point groups as the statistical uncertainty. There are clearly some slow variations that are not statistically random, so a standard deviation of the mean of the over 7000 points is not appropriate. This data is very consistent with the results going back to 1998.

References

- [1] B. P. Kibble, *Atomic Masses and Fundamental Constants*, vol. 5, J.H. Sanders and A.H. Wapstra, Ed. New York: Plenum, p. 545, 1976.
- [2] I. M. Mills, P. J. Mohr, T. J. Quinn, B. N. Taylor and E. R. Williams "Redefinition of the kilogram, ampere, kelvin and mole: a proposed approach to implementing CIPM Recommendation 1 (CI-2005)" *Metrologia* vol. 43, pp.227–46, 2005.
- [3] R. Steiner, E. Williams, D. Newell and R. Liu, "Towards an electronic kilogram: an improved measurement of the Planck constant and electron mass," *Metrologia*, vol. 42, No. 5, pp. 431–441, Sep. 2005.
- [4] R. Steiner, E. Williams, R. Liu and D. Newell, "Uncertainty improvements of the NIST electronic kilogram", *IEEE Trans. on Instrum and Meas.*, vol. 56, no. 2, pp. 592-596, Apr. 2007.

Figure 1. Watt data recorded since Dec. 2005. Each point is the average of a daily run. Error bars are the standard deviation of that day's run. Closed points • are normal data runs, and the solid line is the average of these points. The gray lines are 1 sigma standard deviation of 0.014 $\mu\text{W}/\text{W}$. The open points o are special tests or coincident with extreme environment changes.